

**Relation of Measure of Time Evolution 1- Integral dt (0,T) dt' (0,T)
 $\langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle \langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle$ and Infinite Well Momentum Wavefunction**

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In (1) a measure to determine time evolution of a quantum system is given as:

$$D = 1 - \int_0^T \int_0^T \langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle \langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle dt dt'$$

Using $W(x,t) = \sum_n c_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ (1) shows:

$$D = 1 - \sum_{n,m} |c_n c_m| |c_n c_m| \text{sinc}[\omega_{nm} T/2] \text{sinc}[\omega_{nm} T/2]$$

The authors argue that this measure may be applied to qubit systems. Their result is based on the form $\exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ and the idea of a fixed time interval T.

Here we argue that an identical form appears in the spatial realm for a system which instead of a finite time interval contains a finite length. The relevant system with a finite length is that of an infinite well potential with length L because the wavefunction is 0 outside this length. In such a case, instead of $\exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ we relate $\exp(-ipx) W_n(x)$ to $a(p)$, the momentum wavefunction, and show that measure of time evolution is essentially of the same mathematical form as: $1 - a(p)a(p)$ for an infinite well of length L. $1 - a(p)a(p)$ has the interpretation of the probability not to find a particle in an infinite well in a momentum state of p for a given energy level with average momentum of $n \cdot 3.14/L$.

Time Evolution Measures

In (1), the authors first discuss the idea of a quantum state $W_1(x,t)$ evolving in time into an orthogonal state $W_2(x,t)$. They note this does not always happen or if it does, it may take an infinite amount of time in many cases. They thus propose a different (complementary) measure to capture the idea of time evolution, which they define as:

$$D = \text{evolution measure} = 1 - \int_0^T \int_0^T \langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle \langle W(x,t)|W(x,t') \rangle dt dt' \quad ((1))$$

One may note that both integrals run over the same time interval. Using:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n c_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{One finds: } \langle W(x,t) | W(x,t') \rangle = \sum_n c_n^* c_n \exp(-iT E_n) \quad ((3))$$

Finally:

$$D = 1 - \sum_{n,m} |c_n c_m| |c_n c_m| \text{sinc}[T/2 |E_n - E_m|] \text{sinc}[T/2 |E_n - E_m|] \quad ((4))$$

For $E_n - E_m$ not equal to 0 as shown in (1).

Measure in X Space

We argue that the above time evolution measure is linked to a common measure in x space albeit for a system with a fixed L length instead of a time interval. The infinite well potential system with a length of L as such a system because the wavefunction is 0 outside this length range. In that case:

$$a(p) = \int dx \exp(-ipx) W_n(x) \quad \text{where } W_n(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

$\exp(-ipx)W_n(x)$, however, is of the same mathematical form as: $\exp(-iEnt) W_n(x)$.

In the time evolution case, $W(x,t) = \sum_n c_n \exp(-iEnt) W_n(x)$. For one system, $c_n=1$, and there remains $\exp(-iEnt) W_n(x)$ which is of the identical form as $\exp(-ipx)W_n(x)$.

For an infinite well potential of length L, the integration limits of ((5)) become 0 to L because $W_n(x)$ is 0 outside these limits. (One may consider the limits $-L/2$ and $L/2$ about the origin for symmetry as well.) Formally (2)

$$W_n(x) = \sqrt{2/L} \sin(k_n x) \quad \text{where } k_n = n\pi/L \quad ((6)) \quad n \text{ even} \quad \text{and} \quad \sqrt{2/L} \cos(k_n x) \quad n \text{ odd}$$

Thus one has the full form $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iknx)$, $\exp(iknx)$ making the integral ((5)) very similar to the "Sum" term of ((4)). In fact, defining:

$$D = 1 - \sum_p a(p)a(p) \quad \text{one has: } D = 1 - \sum_p \left\{ \text{sinc}\left(\frac{L}{2}(kn-p)\right) \right\} \left\{ \text{sinc}\left(\frac{L}{2}(kn-p)\right) \right\} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{where } b = \sqrt{L/(3.14 \hbar)} \left(\frac{3.14}{(3.14 + pL/\hbar)} \right) \quad ((8)) \quad \text{with } kn = 3.14 n/L.$$

Thus one may see the similarity between the momentum wavefunction for a particle in a box with infinite walls and the time evolution operator presented in (1). In fact, the time evolution operator is:

$$D = 1 - \sum_p a(p)a(p) \quad ((8)) \quad (\text{with two sums pulled out})$$

Each p is then a different measure which depends on L and $kn=3.14 n/L$. In principle, one may add a Sum over p, n i.e. $D = 1 - \sum_{p,n} a(p)a(p)$ which would cover all p values and kn levels i.e. the ground and excited states.

The form D, however, has a probabilistic interpretation because $a(p)a(p) = P(p)$, the probability for a particle in the box to be in a p momentum state, even though on average its momentum state is $\hbar n \pi / L$. Thus D represents the probability for a particle not to be in a momentum state of p.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in (1) a time evolution measure for a quantum system is introduced. It is given by:

$$D = 1 - \int_0^T dt \int_0^T dt' \langle W(x,t) | W(x,t') \rangle \langle W(x,t) | W(x,t') \rangle$$

Using $W(x,t) = \sum_n c_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$, D is shown in (1) to be equivalent to:

$$1 - \sum_{n,m} |c_n c_m| |c_n c_m| \text{sinc}[T/2 |E_n - E_m|] \text{sinc}[T/2 |E_n - E_m|] \quad n, m \text{ not equal.}$$

Here we show that the form of the time evolution measure also describes mathematically the form $1 - a(p)a(p)$ for a particle in an infinite well, for a given energy level $\hbar k_n = 3.14 n/L$. $a(p)a(p)$ has the physical interpretation of $P(p)$, the probability for a particle to be in a momentum state of p . Thus $1 - a(p)a(p)$ is the probability for a particle in an infinite well not to be in a momentum state of p for a given energy level. Summing over all p yields $D=0$ for a given energy level.

References

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